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THE CASE FOR CONVERGENCE IN AI SAFETY.

Ana Beatriz Duarte

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Policy Statement

This policy brief emphasizes the need for a unified, evidence-based approach to AI safety. Given the inability to fully explain AI decisions, the global community has a growing consensus about the need to prioritize AI safety. However, discussions about AI safety often focus on different topics. While some scholars are alert to the dangers of cyberattacks and even the possibility of AI taking over, civil society experts claim for now-and-here issues such as the military use of autonomous weapons and other present-day risks. Common to the discourse of both groups is the concern with control, diverging in what and how.

Background

This policy brief examines recent discussions on AI safety and regulatory approaches, recommending measures to ensure AI's safe and ethical development. Notably, it highlights the lack of emphasis on autonomous weapons—systems that “select and apply force to targets without human intervention”—in forums focused on AI safety. Discussions tend to center more on the hypothesis of existential threats rather than current concerns.

While AI safety is a primary concern in global governance forums, there is limited consensus on achieving it or what constitutes acceptable trade-offs.

The primary risks associated with AI identified in global governance forums include “misaligned” systems, misuse for malicious purposes, and the concentration of power among many technological entities. Aligning AI with human principles and ethical values remains a shared concern in these discussions.

In 2023, the UK organized the AI Safety Summit in Bletchley Park, where Alan Turing helped break German cryptography during World War II. Following the global negotiations, Seoul held another AI Summit in 2024. In February 2025, Paris hosted the AI Action Summit, the first in the European Union.

These meetings produce both political resolutions and scientific reports.

Although the International Scientific Report on the Safety of Advanced AI, resulting from the summit in the UK, will only be released during the summit in France, a draft version clearly states the need to control general-purpose AI.

The report [i], produced by an expert group chaired by Professor Yoshua Bengio, classifies the risks as either malfunctioning or systemic. These include labor market disruptions, environmental costs, privacy violations, and inequality.

One word could summarize how the group of experts addresses these risks: “control.” The term, used 198 times throughout the UK event report, appears as part of the problem—the lack of it—and as a key part of the solution: “controllability.”

Professor Bengio and another report author, Professor Stuart Russell, were invited as keynote speakers for an event in preparation for the next global AI summit in Paris, the AI Safety Symposium, scheduled for October 2024 at Sorbonne University.

During the preparatory symposium for the global summit in Paris, both keynote speeches emphasized the idea of safe-by-design AI systems, indicating that AI systems should be developed with built-in safety guarantees from the beginning.

Both presenters focused on the possibility that humanity may one day achieve Artificial General Intelligence (AGI). They agreed that AI must align with human values and emphasized the need to ensure human control over it.

Findings

The discussions at the 2024 Safety Symposium in Paris largely overlooked critical issues such as autonomous weapons and other contemporary threats to human rights. While the conversations focused on AI’s alignment with human values, ethical challenges, and governance, they suggest that the debate on AI safety is far from resolved.

Bengio raised concerns about financial incentives affecting AI development, particularly the competitive pressures between countries such as the U.S. and China. He warned that this “AI race” could lead to rapid advancements at the expense of safety as participants rush to build AI systems without addressing these issues.

Russell shared Bengio's concerns about the ethical implications of progressing AGI. Referring to Alan Turing, he asked: How can we ensure these systems align with human objectives? Who decides on these goals? And ultimately, is it ethical to pursue the advancement of AGI? [ii]

In 2023, a plea to slow down AI development made headlines when prominent stakeholders, including several professors, signed an open letter advocating for an "AI moratorium." They supported this idea by citing historical instances where scientists' warnings led to strict safety protocols, such as those in cloning research and the development of nuclear weapons.

Paradoxically, the two researchers appear skeptical about the effectiveness of regulations. Russell argues that current regulations may be ineffective, given the rapid pace of technological evolution. Bengio, on the other hand, believes we need both safety and innovation instead of choosing between the two. He maintains that "the right approach to regulation is not to dictate what must be followed but to establish principles"[iii]. Ensuring human control through safe-by-design AI." He states, "is the most important principle to uphold. Another key principle would be the precautionary principle, which holds that one does not need definitive proof of disaster to take preventive action."

Dan Nechita, the technical negotiation lead for the EU AI Act and keynote speaker, offered a counterpoint. While many in the industry fear that regulation will stifle innovation, he argued that this is a false dilemma. "Proper regulation, especially based on principles like transparency and accountability, can lead to greater trust in AI systems, fostering broader adoption and creating larger markets for AI technologies. Safe, trustworthy AI could drive more innovation by alleviating public concerns and boosting societal confidence in the technology."

Indeed, the discussion about AI regulation must balance government oversight and industry accountability. Regulation, such as the EU AI Act, is as important as incorporating control principles within AI products. Governments and international agreements should not be eclipsed by industry self-regulation; both are crucial for ensuring the safe and ethical use of AI technologies.

As previously mentioned, the Paris symposium neglected immediate safety risks, indicating a limited understanding of AI safety.

Similarly, the presentation text for the Paris AI Action Summit[iii], while showcasing a discourse on inclusivity, multilateralism, intersectoral cooperation, and human rights, the presentation text for the Paris AI Action Summit omits key topics related to these values. This includes, for instance, autonomous weapons and AI warfare, as well as challenges like national sovereignty in the context of concentrated power held by private actors.

Moreover, absent dissenting opinions from notable experts like Yann LeCun restricted the diversity crucial for a comprehensive debate. LeCun and others contend that while AI poses challenges, worries about existential risks are frequently overstated, suggesting a need for more balanced discussions[iv].

In summary, although a comprehensive and inclusive dialogue is crucial for ensuring AI's safe and ethical evolution, this symposium overlooked an opportunity to accomplish this, leaving significant gaps unaddressed.

Recommendations

Based on the previous findings and discussion, we have included below several policy Principles and recommendations states should adopt to anticipate the upcoming AI Action Summit, scheduled for February 2025 in Paris, and subsequent AI policy discussions.

- **Address Autonomous Weapons:** Policymakers must actively engage in discussions regarding autonomous weapons, as their exclusion from primary AI safety debates indicates a significant oversight. Developing these technologies poses substantial risks and should be regulated by international treaties and agreements. Many countries have made clear statements supporting the creation of a legally binding international treaty to prohibit and restrict the production, commercialization, and use of these kinds of weapons, ensuring “meaningful human control” over their use.[v]
- **Promote Safe-by-Design Standards:** AI systems must incorporate safety guarantees from their initial design stages, particularly for high-risk technologies. This means implementing mandatory transparency and accountability mechanisms before market entry, especially for applications with significant societal impact. The standards should also mandate human oversight for any decision-making for military applications.

- **Strengthen Transdisciplinary, Inclusive Research:** A significant increase in research funding and incentives is essential. It should include diverse scientific viewpoints, such as those who contend that AI does not pose existential risks. Engaging with dissenting perspectives will create a more balanced approach to AI safety regulation and foster more prosperous, productive policy outcomes.[vi]
- **Involve the private sector:** Incorporating AI into national security strategies presents unique challenges, as these technologies are often developed by commercial companies that operate outside national security frameworks and evolve faster than government policies can keep pace. Additionally, the specialized expertise needed to evaluate these technologies is concentrated mainly in the private sector. [vii]To ensure that AI technologies meet national security needs, governments should establish a specialized task force composed of experts from both public and private sectors to promote knowledge exchange and foster cooperation between these sectors.

Final Considerations

Explaining AI decision-making processes remains challenging. This is why the need for “safety” continues to require clarification. AI safety is not a universally accepted concept regarding how to achieve it and at what cost, with interpretations and priorities differing significantly.

One mainstream approach is framed as the “alignment and control challenge,” where the risk is located in the future. The best solution would arise from the industry itself, designing AI products that align with human values and ensure safe behavior. The AI research community currently lacks a reliable method to guarantee such alignment. Some important terms for this approach include alignment, safety, control, existential risk, future, humanity, survival, principles, and for good.

Another approach to AI safety—and the one we advocate—centers on risks like privacy violations, surveillance, and the threat posed by “killer robots” (autonomous weapon systems). This community, which includes various civil society organizations, advocates for human-centric and ethical AI development and robust regulatory frameworks. The focus here highlights societal values such as democracy, the rule of law, and fundamental human rights.

Tackling these risks will necessitate worldwide collaboration among nations and a collective effort involving governments, international organizations, industry, and civil society.

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Ana Beatriz Duarte Rodriguez (Universidade de Coimbra; InterAgency Institute): Ana Beatriz Duarte is a Ph.D. candidate in Contemporary Studies at the Univ. Coimbra. She holds a BA in Journalism and a Masters in Social History. Research Associate at InterAgency Institute.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4736-4595>

InterAgency Institute

<https://interagency.institute/>
contact@interagency.institute

Editor-in-chief: Larlecianne Piccolli
